

EO1 DRAFT PROTOCOLS

YOU

YOU wish to publish OA (CC0 license) or beyond OA, venturing into the wild blue yonder of “No Rights”

YOU have no interest in furthering the metrics-driven, academic culture industry and prefer to produce and disseminate your work without concern for mere careerist and/or institutional agendas

YOU prefer to let works speak for themselves and are willing to let works decide where they wish to go and how they are editioned

YOU are willing to transfer your moral rights as author to works

YOU no longer have or never have had any interest in the neoliberal capitalist term *Human Capital* and refuse to leverage your works as private property and/or as commodity

YOU agree that the Republic of Letters (Diderot) and General Intellect (Marx) are hardly the same thing as the neoliberal-capitalist Knowledge Commons

WE

WE are a not-for-profit literary agency established solely for the purpose of assisting authors and artists (and artist-scholars) to produce and disseminate works without any intention of servicing Capital and/or the protocols of the art-academic industrial complex

WE agree that the Republic of Letters (Diderot) and General Intellect (Marx) are hardly the same thing as the neoliberal-capitalist Knowledge Commons

WE wish to help authors and artists (and artist-scholars) publish OA (CC0 license) or beyond OA, venturing into the wild blue yonder of “No Rights”

WE are not an editorial bureau and do not offer editorial services in any conventional sense

WE, as literary agency, wish to promote iterative, aleatory, and collectivist-based works of literary-artistic scholarship

WE will, without reimbursement, assist authors and artists (and artist-scholars) who wish to publish OA (CC0 license) or beyond OA in logistics for the production and dissemination of works

WE advocate the elective abolition of intellectual property rights

December 29, 2023

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